

ELIXIR Core Data Resources & Deposition Databases Selection 2023

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Background

In 2016, ELIXIR introduced the [Core Data Resource](#) (CDR) accreditation process to formally assess, acknowledge and endorse crucial databases within the realm of life sciences. The ELIXIR CDRs constitute a portfolio of European data resources that are of vital importance to the broader life-science community and provide and maintain curated biological data. Complementing the CDRs, the [ELIXIR Deposition Databases](#) (EDD) represent a portfolio of data repositories specifically assessed and acknowledged as the recommended choice for the deposition of a particular type of experimental data. These resource portfolios serve as foundational pillars for research and innovation across a diverse range of biological data types.

The [ELIXIR CDR Selection Criteria](#) include five assessment areas that are used by reviewers to assess whether a resource can be accredited as an ELIXIR CDR:

1. Scientific focus and quality of science
2. Community served by the resource
3. Quality of service
4. Legal and funding infrastructure, and governance
5. Impact and translational stories

Where a resource allows direct deposition of data by the research community and that database is the principal or most comprehensive one in the ELIXIR network for a particular data type, then it may also be eligible for EDD status. Where only the technical quality (3) and governance criteria (4) meet the threshold for CDR status, a resource may be assigned *EDD only* status.

Fourth round ELIXIR CDR & EDD Selection - 2023

ELIXIR ran its fourth round of ELIXIR CDR & EDD selection during 2023. This resulted in:

- 10 new resources being awarded CDR status, bringing the total number of CDRs to 32.
- 4 new resources being awarded EDD status, bringing the total number of EDDs to 16.

The new ELIXIR CDRs & EDDs from the 2023 fourth round selection are listed below:

Resource	Status	Description
BacDive	CDR	BacDive is a bacterial metadatabase that provides strain-linked information about bacterial and archaeal biodiversity. Bacterial diversity includes information on taxonomy, morphology, physiology, and ecology of bacterial strains with genome and other molecular data.
BioStudies	CDR & existing EDD	BioStudies holds descriptions of biological studies, linking to the underlying data, including data that do not fit in the structured archives at EMBL-EBI. It accepts a wide range of study types via a simple format.
EMDB	CDR & existing EDD	The Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB) is a public repository for electron cryo-microscopy maps and tomograms of macromolecular complexes and subcellular structures. It covers a range of techniques, from single-particle analysis to electron tomography.
EMPIAR	EDD only	The Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive (EMPIAR) repository is a public resource for raw images underpinning 3D cryo-EM maps and tomograms. It also accommodates 3D datasets obtained with volume EM techniques and soft and hard X-ray tomography.
GWAS Catalog	CDR & EDD	The NHGRI-EBI GWAS Catalog is a curated collection of all human genome-wide association studies, produced by a collaboration between EMBL-EBI and NHGRI.
HGNC	CDR	The HGNC (HUGO Gene Nomenclature Committee) is a resource for approved human gene nomenclature containing ~42,000 gene symbols and names and 1,300+ gene families and sets.
LIPID MAPS®	CDR & EDD	LIPID MAPS is designed to be an open, systematic and standardised lipidomics resource. Providing information on Lipids and their structures, properties and functions in biological processes.
MGnify	CDR	The MGnify platform facilitates the assembly, analysis and archiving of microbiome-derived nucleic acid sequences. It provides access to taxonomic assignments and functional annotations for nearly half a million analyses covering metagenomic data from a wide range of environments.
ModelArchive	EDD only	ModelArchive stores theoretical models of macromolecular structures and provides unique stable accessions (DOI) for referencing. It also supports the storage of assumptions, parameters and constraints applied in the simulation to make models more reproducible.

PomBase	CDR	PomBase is a comprehensive database for the fission yeast <i>Schizosaccharomyces pombe</i> , providing structural and functional annotation, literature curation and access to large-scale data sets.
SWISS-MODEL	CDR	SWISS-MODEL is a fully automated protein structure homology-modelling server, making protein modelling accessible to all life science researchers worldwide. It is also a repository for models of all the protein sequences for thirteen core species, which are generated every week, based on the latest UniProtKB proteome.
VEuPathDB	CDR	VEuPathDB provides a single point of access to diverse genomic and other large scale datasets related to eukaryotic pathogens and invertebrate vectors of disease. Organisms supported by this resource include (but are not limited to) the US-based NIAID list of emerging and re-emerging infectious diseases.

Reviewers & Evaluators for the ELIXIR 2023 CDR Process

As part of the ELIXIR CDR & EDD Selection Process, resources are reviewed by a minimum of two internal and three external reviewers based on the five assessment criteria. These reviews were subsequently compiled for an internal [ELIXIR Heads of Nodes](#) review panel to deliberate and determine CDR and EDD accreditation recommendations on 25 September 2023. Resources were informed of the review panel recommendations and offered an opportunity to provide a rebuttal. This information was compiled and provided to the ELIXIR Heads of Nodes to decide upon final accreditation outcomes on 7 December, 2023. Final outcomes were publicly disseminated on 14 December, 2023.

External Reviewers

The ELIXIR Hub would like to publicly acknowledge the vital role played by the external bio-data experts in the Core Data Resources & ELIXIR Deposition Database Selection Process.

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ELIXIR Heads of Nodes Reviewers & Selection Panel

The ELIXIR Hub would like to acknowledge the vital role played by all those across the ELIXIR Nodes, in particular the Heads of Node and their delegates that formed a Selection Panel provided in the Core Data Resources & ELIXIR Deposition Database Selection Process.